

NextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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1 Executive summary

The NextGEMS project website has been set up under the domain <https://nextgems-h2020.eu/>. The website is hosted by the project partner Max Planck Institute for Meteorology (MPI-M) and is maintained by the NextGEMS project office.

The website serves as the main dissemination tool to external parties and includes relevant information for project partners. It provides recent news and information on upcoming events, as well as scientific information on the project themes. A particular highlight in terms of communication is the innovative VideoBlog where the first videos are already available and further will follow soon.

The website will grow over time and will be continuously updated with content provided by all project partners. It will be available and accessible throughout the projects lifetime.

2 Conclusion & Results

The website is up and running since the start of the project in September 2021. It provides a base platform for project information and videos / visualizations that are further distributed via social media channels. In the upcoming weeks we will put an emphasis on developing the "Partner Area" and add useful information on accessing and working with the first simulation outputs of Cycle 1.

3 Project objectives

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	no
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|--|-----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | yes |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | yes |

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package:

Objectives of WP1	Relevance in this deliverable?
Day to day project management	yes
Scientific coordination including quality assurance (KPI) and risk assessment	yes
Data management	no
Ensure efficient innovation management, managing exploitation of project results	yes
Supporting communication and dissemination activities	yes
Clustering with EC, regional and international projects/programmes	no

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

This deliverable is part of the major tasks listed under WP1 Tasks 1.5 and directly links to WP10 in supporting the dissemination and communication activities formulated therein.

4.1 Status Quo

We are using the well-known open access content management system (CMS) TYPO3. this CMS is well-established and continuously improved by the community of developers which support the idea of open access. Especially the well-documented rights management system and the security features make it a perfect CMS for the the academic world as well as governmental bodies. There are quite a number of NextGEMS project members which have extensive experience with TYPO3 which allowed us to have a rapid start with our visual presence in the internet.

The basic structure of the NextGEMS website is built around the key areas illustrated in Figure 1 and summarized in the following.

Figure 1: Structure of the NextGEMS project website..

The website is divided in the following sections: About, Research Themes, Outreach (including Vlog), Publications, Events, and Partner area. The 'About' section, contains the general overview of the project, including information about the project objectives and implementation. In "NextGEMS in a Nutshell" the core idea of the project is described, underpinned by quotes of well-known climate scientists and graphics that highlight the innovation in the projects high-resolution model simulations. In parallel, the NextGEMS introductory video clip tells the same story in plain language understandable to stakeholders, politicians, and the public and leads the project website <https://nextgems-h2020.eu/>. A screenshot is included in Figure 2.

Figure 2: NextGEMS project website. The front page shows the introductory clip, the first one of the VideoBlog dissemination strategy (<https://nextgems-h2020.eu/>).

Additionally, we provide information and links to our partner institutes. This structure was chosen following the main standards in website design, and the content described in this first section of the website is static and will always be available.

The second section is 'Research themes', in which each theme (Radiation, Land, Ocean, and Society) has its own section. Currently, there is information about the main goal of the theme, but this section will be continuously updated

with the advancement of the project.

The website section 'Outreach', contains all the work performed under the dissemination activities. This include the NextGEMS VideoBlog (**Vlog**) with the science explainers and the NextGEMS project introductory clip. While the entire project website is a living and evolving entity, the communication tool **Vlog** will be an exciting area exploring the development of the project.

In the section 'Publications' we will collect all publications developing out of the project by all project partners.

Finally, in the 'Events' section, we inform about upcoming events and we report on them afterwards, linking to the 'News' section. The news are visible on the first page (see Figure 3, the most recent one being on the *NextGEMS Art* project where we ask the partners to submit artistic interpretations and visualizations that result from their data evaluation.

Also, we held our first project meeting, the Cycle 1 Hackathon in Berlin. While the scientific results will inform the next Cycle 2 simulations, the hackathon atmosphere is nicely captured in another VideoBlog (Vlog) entry available at <https://nextgems-h2020.eu/events/cycle-1-hackathon>.

Figure 3: NextGEMS news article on the first page of the project website.

The 'Partner area', as the last section of the website, is meant for the project partners to have access to our internal communication and document exchange platforms (see also chapter 9.1 of this report).

4.2 Next Steps

We are searching for supplementary and rational methods to enhance the stability, visibility, the visual and physical attractiveness of the NextGEMS website. In the next months we aim to migrate the current website including it's content to a new design characterized by being intuitive, trustworthy, and responsive. As such, we will reach our target groups, the interested public, policy makers, the press, and students on top of the science-related groups.

The new design shall put our dissemination and communication strategy in form of Vlogs better into focus. A first sketch is provided in Figure 4. Also, a project timeline shall be included similar to the one sketched in Figure 5.

5 References (Bibliography)

NextGEMS project website: <https://nextgems-h2020.eu/>

Figure 4: Sketch of envisioned new website design. By Pajam Sobhani

6 Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

Figure 5: Sketch of envisioned project timeline as part of the new website design.

6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

The website is publicly available. The link to the website will be included in other dissemination activities, such as presentations, reports, or newsletters. In particular, the website will be linked to our posts in other social media channels such as *twitter* (https://twitter.com/nextgems_eu) and *reddit*.

7 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?
no

8 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

No changes required so far.

9 Sustainability

9.1 Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

The current deliverable is strongly linked to all other work packages by stating the project scientific goals. In particular, it provides a central platform for disseminating the Vlog entries in form of science and progress videos related to WP10 (Communication and dissemination plan).

The website includes a *Partner Area* where we link the NextGEMS project to the ESIWACE2 project and the collaboratively developed *easy.gems* platform (<https://easy.gems.dkrz.de>), a "How To" for working with the simulation output.

10 Full track of dissemination activities

- establishing a Mattermost team for internal project communication
- creating a twitter account for the project
- building the main project website (current deliverable)

- holding the Cycle 1 hackathon

11 Full track of publications and IP

Not yet applicable.